

Excited state intramolecular proton transfer in 4-hydroxy-3-formylbenzoic acid at room temperature and 77 K[†]

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The absorption and emission properties of 4-hydroxy-3-formylbenzoic acid (HFBA) have been studied in some nonpolar and weakly polar solvents in relation to 4-methyl-2,6-diformylphenol (MFOH) at room temperature and 77 K. The excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) is evidenced by a large Stokes shifted emission ($\sim 11448\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which is likely to originate from the enol tautomer. The stable molecular structure in the ground state of HFBA is found to be an intramolecularly hydrogen bonded closed conformer from which proton transfer takes place in the first excited singlet (S_1) state. Proton transfer in the ground and excited state of HFBA has also been studied in dioxane/cyclohexane and tetrahydrofuran/cyclohexane solvent mixtures using steady state spectroscopy. At 77 K, HFBA exhibits phosphorescence in dioxane and only in presence of a base in *n*-hexane and 3-methylpenpruetane (3MP). It has been proposed that like MFOH, phosphorescence occurs due to the rotation of the formyl group present in HFBA.

In our previous work we have studied the structures and proton transfer processes of the ground and excited states of 4-methyl-2,6-diformylphenol (MFOH), 4-methyl-2,6-diacetylphenol (MAOH), 4-methyl-2,6-diamidophenol (MDOH), 4-methyl-2,6-dicarbomethoxyphenol (CMOH) and 3-methyl-6-hydroxy-*m*-phthalic acid (HmPA) in different nonpolar and weakly polar solvents¹⁻⁷. Some of the results obtained are as follows : (i) the stable molecular structure in the ground state is an intramolecularly hydrogen bonded closed conformer, (ii) the excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) is evidenced by a large Stokes shifted emission and originates from the enol tautomer of the closed conformer, (iii) at 77 K, the emission spectra of MFOH and MDOH show phosphorescence, whereas MAOH and CMOH do not show any such phosphorescence in nonpolar solvents, (iv) the quantum yields (ϕ_f) of MAOH. MDOH and CMOH are relatively larger than that of MFOH. MFOH, MAOH, MDOH, CMOH and HmPA are chromophores structurally similar to *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (OHBA). Nagaoka *et al.*^{8,9} studied the spectral features and dynamics of some proton transfer processes in different solvents at room temperature and at 77 K. They suggested that the Stokes shifted fluorescence originates from a form of OHBA which is likely to be an enol tautomer. They also showed that phosphorescence is obtained from the open conformer of OHBA.

Due to the absence of solvent perturbation, proton transfer is rapid in nonpolar solvents^{10,11}. The nonpolar

environment offers an excellent opportunity for studying the proton transfer reaction of the unsolvated molecules. The proton transfer of aromatic molecules which are intramolecularly hydrogen bonded in the ground state undergo marked changes depending upon the kind of substituents on the aromatic ring and on the carbonyl group¹²⁻¹⁵. In our earlier work¹⁻⁵, we have observed considerable differences in the absorption and emission spectra of such compounds.

The significant observation about the change in the luminescence property at 77 K and the mechanism of this change seems to merit further investigation. In order to get further information, we have synthesized HFBA with the help of the Inorganic Chemistry department of this institute. In this paper, we have reported the results of the low temperature as well as room temperature spectroscopic studies on HFBA in different nonpolar solvents in relation to the spectral properties of MFOH and MAOH. Nagaoka *et al.*^{9,16} suggested that benzaldehyde type of molecules without intramolecular hydrogen bonding, i.e. the open conformer, is likely to be produced after irradiation in nonpolar solvents at 77 K. It has been proposed that phosphorescence occurs from the open conformer and due to the rotation of the carbonyl group. They observed that the conversion of fluorescence into phosphorescence does not occur in the case of *o*-hydroxy propiophenone (OHPP)⁹ and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (OHAP)¹⁶ in nonpolar solvents, but can take place easily in the case of OHBA¹⁶. Similar

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

observations were also made by us in the case of MFOH and MAOH. We detected phosphorescence in the case of MFOH but not in MAOH in nonpolar solvents^{2,5,17}. The most remarkable observation is that we detected phosphorescence even in the case of MAOH in presence of a strong base like triethylamine (TEA) in nonpolar solvents. It has been suggested that rupture of the intramolecular hydrogen bond is necessary for the formation of open conformer and occurrence of phosphorescence. The structural formula of MFOH and major species of HFBA present in nonpolar and weakly polar solvents are shown in Fig. 1. To get complimentary evidences some studies have been carried out in different solvent mixtures.

Fig. 1. The structural formula of MFOH and major species of HFBA in nonpolar and weakly polar solvents.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra :

The absorption spectra of HFBA exhibit a single broad band at 320 nm (Fig. 2a) in all the nonpolar solvents like *n*-hexane, benzene, 3MP, cyclohexane and CHCl_3 . On the addition of a strong base like TEA, the intensity of 320 nm

band increases sharply and is shifted to 330 nm. The 320 nm absorption band can safely be assigned to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded normal closed form of HFBA (Fig. 1) as reported earlier in the case of MFOH and its derivatives¹⁻⁶. On the other hand, the absorption spectra in dioxane and THF show a single relatively sharp band at 324 nm. However, intensity of 324 nm band in these solvents increases sharply without any change in the position of the band on addition of TEA ($\sim 2.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). It is also observed that on increasing the concentration of dioxane or THF (upto $\sim 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in a cyclohexane solution containing HFBA, the intensity of the band (320 nm) increases and is shifted to 324 nm as observed by the added TEA. The 330 and 324 nm bands are attributed to the formation of different types of hydrogen bonded complexes (A-type, B-type, C-type and D-type) due to the interaction with TEA and THF or dioxane (Fig. 1). It needs to be mentioned here that the absorption spectra of MFOH show a single band at 350 nm in these solvents and remain unchanged by the added base^{1,5}.

Emission spectra :

The emission spectra of HFBA show a large Stokes shifted ($\sim 11448 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) band at 505 nm in all the solvents used here except in dioxane and THF (Fig. 2). On the addition of TEA, the 505 nm band is shifted to 500 nm (Stokes shift $\sim 10303 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with a small increase in intensity as shown in Fig. 2b. The excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) is thus evidenced by a large Stokes shifted emission both in absence and presence of base, in all the solvents except in dioxane and THF. Both the large Stokes shifted 505 and 500 nm bands can be assigned to the formation of type-II and type-III enol tautomers of HFBA, respectively. The emission spectra of HFBA, on the other hand, show a band-peaking around 440 nm both in dioxane and THF. The intensity of 440 nm band increases sharply and is blue-shifted to 430 nm on addition of TEA (Fig. 2b). The 440 and 430 nm bands are predicted to be due to B-type and C-type intermolecularly hydrogen bonded complex, respectively. These hydrogen bonded complexes of HFBA are formed by the interaction with electron donor solvents (dioxane and THF) and TEA. It should be mentioned here that in the case of MFOH, the tautomer band is blue-shifted to form the open conformer on addition of base in all the solvents studied here. In the case of MFOH, dual emission for enol tautomer and hydrogen bonded open conformer has been observed in dioxane and THF^{1,5}. It is also noted that on increasing the concentration of dioxane or THF in cyclohexane solution of HFBA, the intensity of tautomer band gradually decreases. However, the position and shape of the band remain unchanged. We were unable to detect

Fig. 2. Absorption (a : I, II), emission (b : III, IV, V, VI) and excitation (VII) spectra of HFBA; in cyclohexane (III, IV, VII) in absence (I, III) and presence (II, IV) of TEA. $\lambda_{\text{exc.}} = 330 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{mon.}} = 505 \text{ nm}$; $[\text{TEA}] = 2.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Emission spectra in dioxane in (V) absence and (VI) presence of TEA.

any new band upto the concentration of dioxane or THF used here ($\sim 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

It is well established now that ESIPT can take place only as long as intramolecular bond exists in the molecule. Once the intramolecular bond is ruptured by the environmental perturbation, ESIPT can not be observed due to the formation of open conformer. This decrease in intensity of the tautomer band (505 nm) must be due to the rupture of the intramolecular bond in HFBA on interaction with electron donor solvent, dioxane or THF and formation of B-type hydrogen bonded complex (Fig. 1). Although ESIPT can not take place from B-type hydrogen bonded complex, it can take place from A-type hydrogen bonded complex, since the intramolecular bond remains unperturbed by the added TEA. It is pertinent to mention here that the solvent benzene is also a π -electron donor, particularly in a polar environment, i.e. in the excited state. But enol tautomer emission on HFBA remains unaffected in benzene. The excitation spectra of both 505 and 500 nm emission occur in the 325 to 330 nm region (Fig. 2b) and agree well with their respective absorption spectra, i.e. with the normal closed conformer and A-type hydrogen bonded complex. This indicates that the tautomer emission originates directly from their absorbing species. The excitation spectra of both 430 nm and 440 nm emission show two bands at 300 and 325 nm. This indicates the presence of two species in the ground state and emission originates from two different ground state species.

Absorption and emission spectra in solvent mixtures :

To get further information about the species present both

in the ground and excited state, we have examined the effect of solvent composition on the spectroscopic properties of HFBA in binary solvent mixtures of dioxane/cyclohexane and THF/cyclohexane. On increasing the volume percent of dioxane or THF in a cyclohexane solution containing HFBA, the intensity of 320 nm band increases significantly with a small shift at 324 nm (Fig. 3a). This observation indicates the formation of B-type hydrogen bonded complex due to the interaction between the OH proton of HFBA and electron donor solvents. By changing the solvent composition, similarly the enol tautomer band (505 nm) disappears and a new band appears gradually peaking around 440 nm region as shown in Fig. 3b with an isoemissive point at 480 nm. The 440 nm band should be a B-type hydrogen bonded open conformer complex as mentioned earlier. Thus, in the excited state, the tautomer is converted to a hydrogen bonded

Fig. 3. (a) Absorption and (b) emission spectra of HFBA in cyclohexane/dioxane mixture; volume percent of dioxane (a and b) : 0 (0); 1 (30); 2 (40); 3 (50); 4 (60) and 5 (80).

complex simply by the addition of dioxane or THF. Moreover, isoemissive point indicates the existence of equilibrium between the B-type complex and the enol tautomer. Hence ESIPT can not be observed in dioxane and THF due to the rupture of intramolecular bond and formation of hydrogen bonded open conformer. The new band appears in 430–440 nm region on increasing the volume percent of dioxane or THF only. Hence, a D-type hydrogen bonded complex may also be present in this region.

The most interesting observation of this study is that ESIPT can be observed even in presence of a base like TEA. This is due to the presence of COOH group in HFBA and TEA will interact first with the carboxyl proton since it is more acidic than the phenolic proton in non-interacting non-polar solvents. The intramolecular hydrogen bond in HFBA will hence remain unperturbed. Our observation suggests that electron donor solvents like THF or dioxane will react with the phenolic proton, in spite of the presence of the carboxylic group in HFBA. Because of the nonrigidity of the carbon backbones in dioxane and THF, the lone-pair on the oxygen can be oriented favorably to enter into intermolecular hydrogen bond formation with the phenolic proton. This appears to be energetically more favorable than abstraction of the carboxylic proton¹⁸. However, after saturation of all the OH proton, dioxane or THF can then enter into interaction with COOH proton to form the D-type hydrogen bonded complex. Roy *et al.*¹⁸ suggested an unusual specific interaction between some aromatic compounds and solvents like THF using AM1 calculation. They have shown that the process involves increased polarization of the carbonyl π -systems and consequent enhanced electrostatic interaction with electron density distribution in cyclic saturated ethers. We were unable to detect the 440 nm emission band upto the concentration of dioxane (or THF) $\sim 10^{-1}$ mol dm⁻³. However, when the volume percent of dioxane or THF is increased, a new band appears at 440 nm at the expense of 505 nm band. Since the 440 nm band is broad, all types of hydrogen bonded complexes may be present in the 440 nm region. The relative quantum yield values (ϕ_f) of HFBA are quite low compared to those of MFOH and MAOH. The relative ϕ_f values are depicted in Table 1. It should be

mentioned here that the relative ϕ_f value obtained is an average of all energy levels, including those for which the yield is very small or almost zero¹⁹. The decrease in ϕ_f reflects a relatively rapid increase of non-radiative rate²⁰. We were unable to measure the life-time values in our nanosecond instrumental setup. This shows that life-times of HFBA are much shorter than the instrumental response function and decay rates are quite fast in these solvents.

Low temperature spectra at 77 K :

Low temperature emission spectra of HFBA are shown in Fig. 4. The emission spectra of MFOH at 77 K consist of a Stokes shifted fluorescence spectra and a phosphorescence spectra in *n*-hexane and 3MP, whereas MAOH does not show

Fig. 4. (I) Fluorescence, (II, III) phosphorescence and (IV) phosphorescence excitation spectra of HFBA at 77 K; I, II and IV in dioxane; III in *n*-hexane + TEA. Shutter control corrected spectra; $\lambda_{exc.} = 330$ nm.

any phosphorescence in these solvents¹⁻⁴. Like MAOH, HFBA also does not show any phosphorescence on irradiation in pure *n*-hexane or 3MP on lowering the temperature to 77 K. However, on addition of TEA to the solution of HFBA, a weak phosphorescence band appears as shown in Fig. 4. It was shown earlier^{1,4,8,9} that phosphorescence occurs from the open conformer and due to the rotation of the formyl group and rupture of the intramolecular bond is necessary for this purpose. Our observation indicates that pure nonpolar solvent can not rupture the intramolecular bond in HFBA even on lowering the temperature to 77 K; a promoter base is necessary to rupture the intramolecular bond. This observation indicates that the intramolecular bond in HFBA is stronger compared to MFOH. The presence of weak phosphorescence band indicates that only a small amount of intramolecular bond in HFBA has been ruptured at this concentration of TEA ($\sim 2.1 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³) even on lowering the temperature. This further supports the fact that TEA enters into interaction mainly with the COOH group even at this low temperature. However, TEA can in-

Table 1. Relative quantum yield of fluorescence (ϕ_f) of similar compounds

Solvent	MFOH	MAOH	MDOH	CMOH	HFBA
Cyclohexane	0.10	0.16	0.13	–	0.05
<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.08	0.18	–	0.34	0.03
3-Methylpentane	0.10	0.06	0.11	–	0.05
Benzene	0.22	–	0.51	0.39	0.04

teract with the phenolic proton after saturation of the carboxylic proton.

On the other hand, in dioxane or THF at 77 K, HFBA shows a strong phosphorescence band on irradiation as shown in Fig. 4. This indicates that intramolecular bond in HFBA is ruptured due to interaction with the solvent dioxane or THF to form the open conformer. Now the formyl group present in HFBA can rotate easily to show phosphorescence. This further supports the fact that dioxane or THF mainly interacts with the phenolic proton of HFBA. The phosphorescence excitation spectra agree well with the absorption spectra, reflecting that the main species present is the intramolecular hydrogen bonded closed conformer before excitation which is converted to an open conformer at 77 K on excitation.

The presence of phosphorescence seems to indicate the existence of intersystem crossing (ISC) in the proton transfer process of HFBA. It may be suggested here that the triplet $n\pi^*$ aromatic carbonyls are intermolecularly bonded to the solvent molecules. Hence, on excitation, the open conformer of HFBA is likely to be produced (IV, Fig. 1). The phosphorescence life-times (τ_p) of HFBA are significantly increased. The τ_p values in *n*-hexane and dioxane are 3 and 112 ms, respectively. This is consistent with our observations. The ϕ_f values are also significantly increased on lowering the temperature to 77 K. The ϕ_f values obtained at 77 K in *n*-hexane and dioxane are 0.3 and 0.5, respectively. According to Gattermann and Stockburger²¹ and Huang *et al.*²², the increase in ϕ_f indicates an increase in the ISC in the deactivation process.

It was shown earlier that the rotation of the formyl group in all aromatic hydroxy aldehydes can occur if the intramolecular hydrogen bond is ruptured by solvent perturbation on lowering the temperature to 77 K³. Nagaoka *et al.*^{8,9} showed that rotation of formyl group is extremely slow in the case of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (OHAP) and does not take place at all in the case of *o*-hydroxypropionophenone (OHPP) but occurs easily in the case of OHBA in nonpolar and weakly polar solvents. Hence, phosphorescence can occur easily in the case of MFOH and OHBA. This is due to the fact that rotation of the formyl group is strongly perturbed by the larger size of the alkyl group attached to the $>C=O$ group of OHAP, MAOH and OHPP. Moreover, the intramolecular hydrogen bonds in OHAP, OHPP and MAOH are relatively stronger than those in MFOH and OHBA.

Conclusion :

Our studies show that spectral properties of HFBA have

changed significantly by the substitution of COOH group in OHBA. The results show that the energy difference between the keto and enol forms and the magnitude of the Stokes shift are increased considerably compared to those of MFOH and OHBA due to the substitution of a COOH group on the benzene ring. We have identified different hydrogen bonded complexes in addition to the enol tautomer of HFBA in different environmental conditions. The most important observation is that electron donor solvents like dioxane and THF enter into interaction mainly with the phenolic proton in spite of the presence of COOH in HFBA. We observed ESIPT in HFBA even in presence of a base like TEA.

Experimental

MFOH, MAOH and HFBA were prepared in the Inorganic Chemistry Department of this institute in a similar way to that reported earlier^{5,6,23}. The compounds were recrystallized from methanol and dried before use. The solvents, namely, cyclohexane, *n*-hexane, 3-methylpentane (3MP), benzene, chloroform, 1,4-dioxane and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were of spectroscopic grade and were all dried and distilled before use. Analytical grade triethyl amine (TEA) was used as a strong base. All the solvents were checked for their purity by steady state fluorescence measurements.

Absorption and emission spectra were recorded on a Jasco 7850 and Perkin-Elmer MPF 44B spectrophotometer, respectively. The relative fluorescence quantum yields were measured from the area under the emission curve as described earlier¹⁻⁴. The low temperature emission spectra were recorded on a Hitachi F4500 spectrophotometer. The phosphorescence life-times were measured from the decay of phosphorescence intensity with time. The concentration of HFBA was maintained at $\sim 2-4 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³. All other experimental details are the same as reported earlier¹.

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